
D 6.5 Harmonisation guidelines report

Task 6.3 Recommendations for EPCs harmonization
WP6 Harmonising/converging EPCs in Europe

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current lack of harmonisation among Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) approaches in different countries should be avoided for the new generation of EPCs. It can be envisaged that the combination of multiple tools and the adaptation to each country/region will result in a large number of EPC schemes; but a comparable level of high quality must be ensured.

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) does not mandate identical EPCs across all regions. Before advocating for harmonization, it's essential to clarify what harmonization means in this context, identify areas where it already exists, examine the motivations behind it, and explore practical ways it could be implemented. Achieving this goal poses unique challenges due to varying building stocks, climate conditions, available technologies, market structures, training and education of EPC issuers and cultural attitudes toward energy use and buildings across different countries.

crossCert proposes a comprehensive set of guidelines for harmonising EPCs, paving the way for improved comparability, transparency, and ultimately, a more energy-efficient building stock in the EU. Based on the testing and assessment of the current and new EPC approaches, recommendations for the EPC harmonisation are provided considering the several EPC dimensions: technical performance, data exploitation and human factor.

CrossCert's journey to investigate the convergence of European Energy Performance Certificates began with the capitalisation of previous European experience and cross-testing among countries, and culminated in harmonisation guidelines that place significant emphasis on the human factor, whether it be the public, auditors, or policymakers.

The findings highlight the necessity of harmonising EPC input parameters, methodologies, and databases across Europe. Recommendations included the creation of georeferenced, open-access databases for EPC data, a more unified approach to handling building-specific inputs like thermal bridges and user behaviour, and improved training for EPC issuers, particularly for those using dynamic models.

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1 Introduction

Under a common general framework for the calculation of energy performance of buildings established by the EPBD in 2002 and further evolved in 2010, Member States developed their own assessment methods, giving rise to the lack of convergence across the EU.

Harmonisation exists at different scales and at different points in the EPBD and its implementation. What do we mean by harmonisation when applying something to so many different countries? Do we just want harmonisation of primary goals (e.g., consistent rating system) but then accept significant differences elsewhere? Or the energy bands themselves? Or the full set of metrics? Taking the complete EPC journey (inputs used, calculation, assessment, assessors, outputs generated, use with national policies), what harmonisation are we particularly interested in?

Once we have defined what level of harmonisation we are interested in, why might we suggest this is a good thing? What is the driver for achieving a certain type of harmonisation – to allow for comparison of buildings/standards across countries? To make implementation of new EPC innovations (e.g., SRI (Smart Readiness Indicator, next-gen metrics) more achievable and consistent? To better standardise the EPC rating itself so that it is a universally recognised output across Europe?.

Whatever the answer to the above, we accept there will be some specific issues in individual countries that limit harmonisation and might even make harmonisation harmful to achieving local/national targets. When faced with different climates, technologies (particularly heating vs. cooling), housing stocks, assessor workforce, policies, and energy behaviour/culture, where does harmonisation make it more difficult for a country to reflect this diversity? For next-generation EPCs, we cannot expect all changes to be adopted by different countries in the same way (due to the above differences). There is not one universal EPC method (that we can simply update for all countries at the same time in the same way), but we want to avoid having many different countries having to individually update their EPCs in different ways. Could EPC approaches be categorised in a useful way so that group of countries can receive similar advice? So, for example, countries using a very tailored and data-heavy approach to EPC assessment could adopt a next-gen metric or other innovation in a similar way – but this may be different to how countries using very standardised/simplified assessments adopt that same innovation.

Jenkins, D. Heriot Watt University 2024

2 Harmonisation on Directive 2024/1275

The update to the DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL regarding the energy performance of buildings (EPBD) aligns with the EU's Green Deal, aiming to decarbonise buildings, lower energy costs, and enhance the quality of living and working environments. Additionally, the initiative supports energy independence under the REPowerEU Plan and encourages sustainable business within the building sector. The directive introduces measures to boost energy efficiency, particularly in poorly performing buildings, and updates EPCs with standardised EU-wide criteria to help citizens make informed financing choices.

In addition to implementing renovation requirements and upgrading the construction standard, the EPBD strengthens the enabling framework and offers new or greater benefits to people in terms of financial help, information, and advice.

According to Article 19, Article 20, Annex V, and Annex VI on improved EPCs, EPCs are a crucial instrument for informing the public about a building's energy efficiency. The EPC framework is greatly enhanced by the Directive.

Member states must make sure that the "appropriate distribution of energy performance indicators" is maintained between the "B" and "F" classes and must **recalibrate the EPC classes using just the letters "A" through "G."** It is imperative for Member States to guarantee that the definition of class limits, or upper and lower thresholds, prevents the emergence of excessively tiny or big classes. This will guarantee a fair distribution of buildings among the classes, allowing Member States to promptly choose which buildings should be given priority for renovation projects.

Some EPC classes should be commonly used across Member States:

- 'G' class should cover the very-worst-performing buildings (defined at national level).
- 'A' class should correspond to ZEB.
- 'A+' class, if Member States decide to use it, should be defined at the national level as "building with a maximum threshold for energy demand which is at least 20% lower than the maximum threshold for ZEB, and which generates more renewable energy on-site annually than its total annual primary energy demand".

Figure 1. Recalibration of EPC classes

As of May 29, 2026, newly issued EPCs should be subject to the revised scale. One exception exists: Member states may delay the rescaling until December 31, 2029, if they rescaled their EPCs between January 1, 2019, and summer 2024 (the time the EPBD came into effect). However, rescaling is not the sole aspect of reforming EPCs. Although the Directive has made numerous improvements to the quality of its material, given the provisions on EPC implementation, the enhancement potential will not be fully realised.

EPCs shall communicate energy performance in a common way – i.e. with numeric indicators of both primary and final energy use in kWh/m²/year – and include, for comparison purposes, reference values (MEPS, NZEB, ZEB). The Directive also introduces **a common EPC template**, to be mandatorily used as of 29/05/2026 specifying which elements the EPC should include.

3 Capitalisation of European experience: Highlights from five projects

CrossCert has reviewed all the European projects that were implemented before or in parallel to crossCert. Five (5) of them have already something to tell regarding **harmonisation**:

ALDREN, ALliance for Deep RENovation in Buildings (2017). The ALDREN energy rating and targets aim to provide in the ALDREN European common certificate (ALDREN EVC) a transparent and comparable metric and more accurate results closer to the actual energy consumption. The ALDREN EVC is compatible with the EPBD requirements on the energy performance certificate. The reliability of the ALDREN approach is based on the following key components:

- Harmonised and transparent calculation methodology based on the new European standards developed under the Commission Mandate M/480, that provides the results closer to the actual consumption using the hourly calculation step, the climate conditions of building location, the real performance of systems and envelope.
- Two main common indicators for the benchmark on the common scale based on the non-renewable primary energy use either (a) with only the self-used PV electricity produced on-site taken into account or (b) including also the export to the grid (the main energy performance indicator).

The harmonisation requests would be met by applying the developed modules, as they are based on CEN and ISO standards.

A consistent, harmonised, unique European energy performance rating, based on ISO/CEN standards, offers comparability and transparency across the EU. Nevertheless, national adaptations will have to be made in order to meet the national legal requirements.

Figure 2. ALDREN’s project EPC format proposal based on ISO/CEN standard

EUBSuperHub European Building Sustainability performance and energy certification Hub (2021)

The Deliverable 1.3 of this project produces recommendations and reference strategies for improving the framework conditions for implementing next generation EPCs, based on literature review and stakeholder interviews, organised according to the project's key concepts of improvement, extension, harmonisation, and reliability.

Recommendations drawn from the literature analysis

All European countries show a disparity in the level of national EPC requirements. Some countries want to see changes those others have been introducing for many years, such as the obligation of an EPC for buyers and owners with the display mandatory of the energy label, climate label and estimated bill. In these countries, which are used EPCs and their regular adaptation, a scalable policy to allow time for owners to react and for public authorities to estimate the necessary support has been recommended.

More broadly, the common recommendations proposed, integrating the elements included in some national EPCs:

- Provide guidance for EPCs - Provide instruments for the cooperation between Countries, State and Regions.
- Provide additional training for EPC auditors and ensure that only officially approved and verified software can be applied for certification.
- Provide a renovation strategy
- Provide more tailor-made recommendations for the cost-effective renovation of buildings.

Recommendations drawn from the interviews regarding the EU building passport

- An EU building passport should be a common tool supported by technically sound EN standards.
- The EU building passport should be comparable with EU building passports of other countries by using harmonised conversion factors and other common conventions and methods.
- Complexity in the EU building passport should be avoided.
- A good compromise/balance between accuracy (preferred by researchers and engineers) and simplicity (usually preferred by practitioners and end-users) should be found.
- The EU building passport should be an instrument, which is easy to fill and to update, in which artificial Intelligence could be used to simplify and automate their filling, using, for example, data from the examined buildings that already exist (EPCs, BIM data, information about renovation, etc.).
- The European passport could be enriched with information on sustainability performance, retrofit actions carried out, construction materials used, running costs, etc.

Consequences in terms of recommendations and suggestions

- Establish clear guidelines for creating an EU building passport, including the EPC.
- Define what comparability truly means and under which conditions it applies.
- Facilitate comparison through the use of graphs, ratings, and rules.
- For harmonised EPCs and building e-passports in the EU, write technical specifications for each national database hosting EPCs and possibly passports. Ensure each database is built on the same architecture and data organisation, provides public access to data (excluding private occupant data), and has the capacity to send information to a central web platform upon request in a defined and strictly harmonised format (XML).
- Harmonise data quality rules and training quality across Europe.
- Organise meetings where Member States can share experiences and feedback, benefiting less mature Member States and helping to equalise skills across countries.

QualDeEPC (High-quality Energy Performance Assessment and Certification in Europe Accelerating Deep Energy Renovation) aimed to improve both the quality and the cross-EU convergence of EPC schemes, as well as the link between EPCs and deep renovation.

The project's outcomes and in particular the deliverables D5.3 '[Guidebook for improved EPCs presenting the project's proposal for an enhanced and converging EPC assessment and certification scheme](#)' and D7.2 '[Conclusive policy recommendations guide](#)' could be considered of high policy interest and could contribute to both the improvement of the EU policy framework (EPBD) and to an enhanced implementation of EPC schemes in the EU, especially in the countries targeted. (BG, DE, EL, HU, LV, ES, SE). The policy recommendations particularly target the link between EPCs and deep (energy) renovation, while increasing the levels of ambition and convergence across the EU in terms of building renovation.

U-Cert has aimed at facilitating convergence of quality and reliability of national procedures, leveraging the set of Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) Standards. During the project implementation, the project mapped and characterised in detail the existing situation regarding EPB Assessments and Certification schemes in the 11 Member States. Such analysis revealed that despite the mandate made by Directive 2018/844/EU [REF], the majority of Member States have not produced or published their respective National Annexes.

The lack of National Annexes is, to the view of U-CERT's consortium, one of the main obstacles to the cross-country comparison of the EU's building stock energy efficiency.

Once the national status was characterised, U-CERT moved to crafting a proposal for a harmonised calculation methodology for EPB Assessments fully aligned with the complete set of EPB Standards.

EPC4EU project - Harmonisation of datasets of Energy Performance Certificates of buildings across Europe (2019- 2021)

EPC approaches in Spain and Italy were analysed, particularly with respect to the datasets generated by current EPC approaches. EPC4EU designed, implemented and tested an EPC data model reusable across the EU to harmonise heterogeneous EPC datasets produced at national/regional level. EPC datasets contain location data related to energy consumption and energy efficiency, which are at the same time semantically rich and spatially detailed (at building level).

In conclusion, regarding the re-usability of the EPC4EU methodology in other Member States, the following lessons have been learnt:

- One of the main problems encountered to adapt the EPC4EU target data model to the Spanish EPC scheme was the **terminology** used. Although the EPCs of both countries (ES and IT) are based on the EPBD, the names of the different parameters contained in the EPCs do not always match precisely or do not always refer exactly to the same element or the same units. In addition, the issue related to the different language issue has to be also taken into account. It was, therefore, necessary to study both models carefully to perform the adaptation. These particularities were also seen in the different code lists, which had to be adapted due to the particularities of the EPC in the different countries.
- Another important problem was the **lack of geo-localised** information present in the Spanish EPC. This problem was solved by combining the information from the EPCs with information from the Spanish cadastre, which, thanks to its adherence to INSPIRE, helped fill in other information in the target model not found in the original Spanish EPC.

4 Cross-testing – Exploring the differences and similarities

Recommendations for EPC harmonisation were derived based on the cross-testing experience. The testing provided insights and recommendations for improving and standardising EPCs throughout Europe and was organised in three rounds.

1st round of cross-testing: Experts tested EPC methodologies from other countries, revealing differences in national approaches to the EPBD. This made it possible to identify key variations and assess whether harmonisation should be applied to groups of similar countries or whether recommendations can be more generally made.

In the **2nd and 3rd rounds of cross-testing**, the focus was in assessing the extent to which the proposed new procedures will redress the deficiencies encountered in the current generation of EPC procedures. The following aspects were addressed:

- The likelihood that the new proposals will improve the performance gap and increase the robustness of existing EPCs
- The new Key Performance Indicators introduced by the next generation certificates, and how they will increase the functionality of EPCs and facilitate the embodying of added value services (investor needs, energy audits, logbooks, building renovation passports, one-stop shops)
- The improvement of the user experience for all types of users (building owners and tenants, buyers, sellers, facility managers, architects, real estate brokers, EPC issuers)
- **The harmonisation of EPCs across Europe, including that of regulations, input and output parameters, EPC verification, EPC databases, training**

4.1 Insights from Cross-testing: A Country-by-Country Comparison

4.1.1 1st Round

In the 1st cross-testing round, experts from one EU country tested the methodology of other countries allowing the consortium to obtain relevant conclusions regarding the harmonisation of certificates.

One result that should be highlighted is the observed reasonable consistency in the energy classification across EPC methodologies.

The labels standardise the numerical values obtained, harmonising the results among countries. Despite the relevant differences in the methodologies, when the labels obtained for the same building are compared using methodologies from different countries, good consistency is observed in the certification methodologies. A building with a high energy rating in one country would obtain a similar rating with the methodology of another country. The same is true for buildings with low energy ratings. This result is very relevant when defining common building renovation policies in the EU based on the energy classes of the building stock. The labels standardise the numerical values obtained, harmonising the results among countries.

Climate data

Certification methodologies, except for the UK's, typically do not allow customisation for local climates. Instead, issuers must select from predefined weather data relevant to the building's geographical area, which can lead to inaccuracies in energy consumption assessments. This approach simplifies the process and enhances comparability but may overlook local climate variations, increasing the performance gap and the perception that EPCs misrepresent actual energy usage. A prior procedure matched buildings with similar climates for more accurate cross-testing.

Language and terms

Language and terminology differences are significant barriers in EPC procedures across countries like Austria and Slovenia. Diverse terms such as "heat energy demand" and "specific site reference energy demand" lack clear definitions, leading to confusion in calculations. For instance, energy consumption metrics differ markedly between countries, with Greece and Croatia excluding lighting energy in residential EPCs, while Spain includes it but omits energy for heating pumps. These inconsistencies highlight the need for harmonisation of terms and indicators to enhance comparability across European EPCs.

Understanding EPC methodologies

Understanding the EPC methodologies of other countries has been a fundamental barrier in the first round of cross-testing. Most of the EPC methodologies are based on static models (they provide results with an annual resolution), except in the case of the UK for non-residential buildings, where a dynamic model is used (they offer results with temporal resolutions of, for example, one hour) and the case of Bulgaria, where a static model is used which is calibrated with actual energy consumption data.

However, even though the same type of model is used in most countries, the hypotheses considered by each country, the **specific procedure** and the **level of detail required in the input data vary considerably** among countries.

The following factors or parameters are the **main source of discrepancies** among the methodologies of different countries:

- Thermal bridges.
- Lightning.
- Orientation of the walls and shadows on the façades.
- Pumping systems.
- Domestic hot water.
- Heat losses in distribution pipes.
- User behaviour.
- Ventilation rates.
- The definition of air conditioning systems.
- Single-zone vs. multi-zone.
- Drawings.
- Surface areas.
- Cooling demand.
- U-values.
- Internal gains.
- Conversion factors.

The diversity of input data has created significant challenges for cross-testing EPC methodologies across countries. Differences in requirements, such as the need for building drawings or lighting data, hinder collaboration. To address these issues, understanding each methodology's calculation and input needs is essential. Additionally, gathering missing information from building owners or making estimations is necessary. The process has taken longer than anticipated, highlighting that cross-testing involves more than data exchange. Developing a neutral inventory format has helped, but compiling a comprehensive dataset remains a complex task.

Static, dynamic versus calibrated models

Most of the EPC methodologies are based on static models (they offer results with an annual resolution). It is observed that the requirements of input data and training of the certifier are much exacting in the case of dynamic and data-calibrated models. Since the next generation of energy certificates tends to incorporate dynamic models or models with data calibration, these issues should be borne in mind. The data requirements and complexity for such models are much higher than those for current static models, and therefore so are the training requirements.

Default values

Default values are integral to energy certification processes, offering benefits such as aiding decision-making, reducing time and costs, and standardising procedures for better comparisons. However, they can lower accuracy by not reflecting actual building conditions and may lead to insufficient training for certifiers. Furthermore, participants in cross-testing noted a lack of clarity regarding these values, and their use can hinder harmonisation across methodologies due to variations based on national regulations. This discrepancy in default values has been a significant concern among partners involved in the cross-testing.

Certification results – better than expectations

The cross-testing of EPC methodologies revealed greater consistency in results across Europe than anticipated, despite initial concerns about discrepancies. While energy demand for heating showed reasonable correlation, factors such as regional climate variations impacted results. Conversely, primary energy consumption and CO₂ emissions exhibited poor correlation due to differences in calculation methodologies and energy system compositions. **However, the alignment of energy class labels across countries indicates that high or low energy ratings are comparable**, aiding in the formulation of EU-wide building renovation policies and promoting standardisation among methodologies.

Indicators and Scales

A significant diversity of metrics and scales has been observed through the cross-testing. Primary energy consumption and CO₂ emissions are the most common indicators presented by EPC methodologies across Europe. However, such indicators may not be the most meaningful for building owners. The metrics and scales show the lack of harmonisation of EPCs across Europe. The variety of metrics makes it difficult to compare among countries.

EPC databases

The accessibility to the EPC databases is very diverse, one of the reasons why further access to data is not allowed in some countries is data privacy.

The different considerations of certificate data privacy in each country must be highlighted since access to certificate information changes significantly in the countries that have participated in crossCert activities. Harmonising access to EPC databases and how to deal with EPC data privacy is a potential recommendation for the next generation of EPCs.

An important aspect of the next generation of energy certificates will be access to certificate data through open (and possibly georeferenced) databases. Currently, this access is far from widespread, but there are countries where the certificate databases almost meet already the expectations for databases of the next generation of EPCs.

4.1.2 2nd Round

Assessment and testing the results of sister projects was done in the 2nd round of cross-testing. Of great importance are the outcomes of testing the projects U-CERT and X-tendo. Both projects contribute to improving and standardising EPC processes, but face challenges in harmonising specific areas like comfort assessment.

Main outcomes of U-CERT

Harmonised Calculation Methodology: U-CERT emphasises the need for an EU-wide software kernel to standardise energy performance calculation methodologies across Europe. This would promote harmonised application of EPB standards and align national building performance calculations.

Open-Source Software: The project supports the development of open-source dynamic energy simulations tools. These tools aim to facilitate hourly energy calculations, grid load, and demand response analyses, providing more accurate energy performance assessments.

Quality Checks: U-CERT recommends performing quality checks on calculation methods, using European standards as the reference, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of EPC data

Main outcomes of X-tendo

Indoor Comfort Level Methodology: X-tendo developed a method to assess indoor comfort levels for both new and existing buildings. Two ratings are available: an **operational rating (CORP)** for buildings in use and an **asset rating (CARP)** for unoccupied or new buildings. Due to limited access to usage data, the CARP method was used in cross-testing. The findings showed that harmonising comfort assessment across Europe may be challenging due to significant variations in comfort criteria, which are influenced by national climates and standards.

4.2 Challenges in harmonising energy performance certificates methodologies

The examination of the diverse EPC methodologies used by CrossCert partner countries, highlighted key differences that affect cross-country comparisons and the cross-testing process. The EPC assessment methods vary widely across Europe, presenting challenges for cross-country harmonisation. The **balance between tailored and standardised approaches** affects how comparable EPC ratings are across countries, and education requirements for assessors also differ significantly.

Key aspects such as regulations, assessor qualifications, and the steps involved in EPC assessments vary widely between countries. Some countries rely on **actual data from site visits** and building documentation, while others **use databases** or allow assessors to make **estimations** based on their professional judgement. These differences can lead to varying results for the same building depending on the assessor.

The use of **standardised input parameters**, such as occupancy and equipment schedules, differs across countries, which can influence EPC results. While **standardising** these inputs could improve **comparability**, it might also **increase the performance gap** – the difference between calculated and actual energy consumption.

Table 1. Summary of the comparison of calculation inputs across crossCert countries

	HVAC schedules	HVAC specification	Lighting and equipment schedules	Occupancy	Construction thermal parameters	Ventilation rates	Infiltration rate	Setpoints
Austria	Default based on building type	Default values available	Default values	Default values	Database available	Database available	Default values available	Fixed
Bulgaria	Assessor	Actual values	Assessor	Assessor	Database available	Measurement/assessor's knowledge	Measurement/assessor's knowledge	Assessor
Denmark	Assessor	Default values available	Default values	Default values	Database available	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control
Greece	Default based on zone activity type	Default values available	Default values	Default values	Database available	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control
Malta	Default based on zone activity type	Default values available for some building categories	Default values	Default values	Database available/ Inference based	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control
Poland	Assessor	Default values available	Default values or assessor	Assessor	Database available but outdated	Database available	Default values available	Depends on use type/activity level/control
Slovenia	Default based on zone activity type	Actual values	Default values	Default values or assessor	Database available	Database available	Measurement/assessor's knowledge	Depends on use type/activity level/control
Spain	Default based on building type	Actual values	Default values	Default values	Database available/ Inference based	Database available	Default values available	Fixed
UK	Default based on zone activity type	Default values available for some building categories	Default values	Default values	Database available/ Inference based	Database available	Default values available for some buildings	Depends on use type/activity level/control

The study also faces limitations due to language barriers, as most EPC methodologies are available only in local languages. Despite these challenges, the report concludes that EPC approaches fall on a spectrum from highly standardised to more tailored methods. Most partner countries favour a standardised approach, with exceptions like Bulgaria, which uses a tailored system where assessors have more freedom

in choosing input values. This flexibility could reduce the performance gap but complicates cross-country comparisons. Poland and Slovenia also allow some tailoring, whereas the UK and Denmark follow a more uniform process.

In terms of assessor qualifications, Bulgaria and Croatia have the highest education and experience requirements, which aligns with their more tailored EPC methodologies. In contrast, countries like the UK and Denmark have less stringent requirements. There is no clear relationship, however, between the level of assessor qualification and the degree of standardisation in a country's EPC approach.

4.3 Investigating the performance gap: energy consumption discrepancies in EPCs

CrossCert investigated the "Performance Gap," which refers to the discrepancy between modelled and actual energy consumption in buildings, focusing on EPCs from nine European countries across 65 buildings. The study compares EPC modelled energy consumption with real metered data, converting EPC outputs as needed to enable comparison.

Key findings reveal that the performance gap is lower for more tailored EPC methodologies than for standardised ones.

The performance gap across countries varies significantly, ranging from 0.77% to 859%. Several factors influence this gap, including the type of building, the chosen EPC methodology, and the categories of energy consumption considered. Some EPC methods do not account for occupant behaviour, further complicating the comparison between modelled and actual energy use. Additionally, different national EPC approaches often have output metrics that hinder direct performance gap comparisons.

The study points out the lack of uniformity in how countries record energy consumption on EPCs. Different **categories of energy** (e.g., lighting, cooling, and electrical appliances) are either **included or excluded from EPC calculations** depending on the country, making performance gap comparisons complex. For instance, the absence of sub-metered data for most countries prevents a precise comparison of energy consumption categories listed in the EPCs, further contributing to the gap. These variations, particularly for non-residential buildings, where electrical equipment and lighting account for significant energy use, underscore the challenges in harmonising EPC methodologies across Europe.

The following figure shows the performance gaps in the different partner countries and the degree of standardisation.

Figure 3. Comparison of the performance gap across crossCert countries

4.4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

crossCert analysed new scales and KPIs for EPCs providing a detailed examination of recent advancements in Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) designed to improve the accuracy and relevance of energy performance assessments and explored how these KPIs are applied across different partner countries. Various KPIs were explored across **five key categories: energy performance, climate change, financials aspects, smartness, and human-centric considerations.**

KPIs dominate the front page of EPCs, with 44 indicators noted across different countries. Climate change-related KPIs, such as those tracking CO₂ emissions, are the second most common, followed by financial KPIs. Interestingly, smartness and human-centric KPIs are less prominent or missing entirely, possibly due to ongoing development in these areas. The countries with the highest number of front-page indicators are Bulgaria and Greece (11 each), while Spain and Malta have the fewest (2 each). Financial KPIs appear only in Denmark and the UK, while Poland and Malta use a color scale instead of letter grades for energy classes. Denmark and Scotland are noted for adopting a more human-centric approach, where the EPC's layout emphasises explanations and readability, making it easier for users to understand and act on the recommendations.

Each of the five categories of KPIs is important and should be considered together rather than separately. crossCert suggests that EPCs should present a holistic view of a building's performance, combining key information on energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, comfort, intelligence, and financial aspects. This integrated approach would make EPCs more useful and accessible to building owners, helping to drive the implementation of energy-saving measures and improvements.

4.5 The format and the nature of recommended improvements in different EPCs

The comparison of crossCert countries' strategies in implementing EPC recommendations highlighted variations in the presentation format of these recommendations. In Austria, Malta, and the UK, recommendations are provided in a separate report, while in other countries, they are integrated into the EPC.

There is a noteworthy divergence in the level of detail provided for recommendations and their impacts on energy, carbon emissions, and cost savings across different countries. For instance, Malta, Poland, and Slovenia outline improvement measures without specifying the associated savings amounts, unlike other countries that include such information with varying degrees of detail.

Moreover, like the distinctions in calculation methodologies discussed in previous crossCert project reports, the approaches to recommendations differ in terms of standardisation. Some countries provide assessors with lists of standardised improvement measures for selection or embed them in the EPC software for automatic integration. Conversely, other countries rely on assessors with suggesting measures based on their own expertise.

4.6 Comparative study of parameter variations and methodological approaches on energy consumption

In the 1st round of cross-testing in the crossCert project, different EPC methodologies were applied to the same buildings to compare various aspects of the methodologies as well as the assessment results. The countries were paired together based on HDD (heating degree days) and CDD (cooling degree days) values.

The testing reports resulting from this round of testing show that between these methodologies, input parameters can vary significantly, in terms of how they are defined (default or tailored values for each building), as well as their numerical values. In addition, variations exist in the general methodology

approaches, such as calibrating models to measured energy data, using dynamic simulations, inclusion of different energy consumption categories, etc.

Bulgaria's comparisons with countries like the UK, Greece, and Spain show some of the lowest differences in final energy consumption results. However, this is primarily due to Bulgaria's calibration step, where assessors adjust the model based on actual energy consumption data or EPC values, rather than methodological similarities. For other countries, comparisons like Spain-Greece and Denmark-Croatia show the lowest differences, suggesting more similarity between their methodologies.

While these results are informative, more case studies are needed to generalise the findings to a broader building stock. The numerical results should also be viewed in the context of the specific EPC methodologies applied in the case studies, which illustrate known differences between countries' approaches.

This further illustrates the divergent approaches to EPC generation amongst the target countries, and the difficulty in comparing such bespoke, country-specific methodologies to buildings outside of the original, targeted geographical region.

Figure 4. Average differences between C-testing results

5 Convergence at the technical level

5.1 Proposed harmonised verification framework for quality checking EPC outputs

Harmonising EPC methodologies and quality control mechanisms across Europe requires careful consideration of differences in both methodologies and workforce qualifications. Countries vary in their approach to quality control – some rely on automatic validation within EPC software, while others use independent manual checks. Standardised methodologies, like those in the UK, Denmark, Austria, and Spain, allow for more automated controls, whereas tailored methodologies, such as Bulgaria's, often need manual expert review.

Table 2. Current approaches in quality control in crossCert countries

	Standardisation rating (1-highly tailored, 5-highly Standardised)	Software validation rules	Database automatic controls	Organisations in charge of independent checks
Austria	5	A list of errors and explanations about them. No warnings about out-of-range values	In some regions in Austria, the EPC database is used for independent quality checks	Performed by relevant energy agencies
Bulgaria	1	Some of the input fields have limits, but the allowed range is wide	Not automatically checked; however, the certificates are checked by the relevant authority before being lodged on the database	SEDA
Croatia	4	There are some checks on inputs and results. No warnings about out-of-range values.	There are no quality controls on the EPC database	The Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets
Denmark	4	Input parameter validation measures	The EPC database is equipped with automatic data validation. It is automatically compared with other building data.	The Danish Energy Agency
Greece	4	Input parameter validation measures	Automatic validity check of EPC data is performed on the national EPC registry platform.	The Ministry of Energy
Malta	5	Input parameter validation measures	The data is thoroughly checked and cleaned before being lodged	The Malta Competition and Consumer Affairs Authority (designated by the Building and Construction Authority (BCA))

Poland	2	No validation measures	The EPC registry automatically checks for missing data; however, there are no automatic checks for the validity of EPC data.	An independent body
Slovenia	3	Input parameter validation measures	The electronic EPC registry runs an automatic check on the EPCs	the Inspectorate of the Republic of Slovenia on behalf of the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning
Spain	4	Limited validation measures (mostly focused on missing inputs for the technical systems) are implemented, No warnings about out-of-range values.	Some automatic checks including various identifiers, date of issue, the length of time between the site visit and EPC issue date, useful area, energy rating typology and negative final energy values	Varies regionally, the relevant institution (Autonomía) in each region
UK	5	Highlights out-of-range values	In-built validation rules applied: use of accredited software, missing fields, out-of-range values, parameter formats, consistency, and controlling the trends of data	Accreditation Schemes The Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities

CrossCert's proposed framework suggests that quality control should be adapted to each country's EPC methodology, software, document structure, and assessor qualifications. **Standardised systems** benefit from **automated software checks**, while **more complex methodologies** need **detailed manual verification**. The type of software used also plays a role, with non-accredited systems requiring stricter manual checks. In countries with simpler EPC documents, automated checks are effective, while more detailed documents may need comprehensive manual reviews.

Assessor qualifications also vary, and quality control should address these differences. Countries with **less qualified assessors might need targeted checks** for lower qualifications, while countries with a highly trained workforce can rely on random inspections to ensure EPC accuracy.

5.2 Framework for next-generation EPCs: Addressing challenges and criteria for harmonisation

crossCert's proposed framework for next-generation EPCs introduces six key criteria:

1. alignment with reality,
2. quantifying new metrics,
3. accommodating new technologies,
4. suitability for punitive policy action,
5. extrapolating and standardising, and the
6. quality of input information.

These criteria aim to address the challenges in harmonising EPC methodologies across Europe, given the varied goals and innovations within EPC frameworks.

Innovations like the Smart Readiness Indicator, dynamic renovation pathways, and new calculation methodologies are expanding the scope of EPCs. Future EPCs are likely to serve more goals beyond basic energy or carbon metrics, which could lead to greater variation between countries' approaches. This evolution introduces complexities in assessment methods and dissemination of information, making harmonisation across Europe more difficult.

A systematic approach should be applied to distinguish between EPC methods, allowing for meaningful comparisons between systems with similar goals. It also suggests that the range of EPC innovations and new user requirements make it unlikely that further changes will enhance harmonisation.

When applying the framework to nine EPC methods – four existing and five next-generation – the study finds no single method excels across all criteria. There is a trade-off between the detail of building assessment and the feasibility of widespread adoption. More detailed assessments offer better accuracy but are harder to implement at scale, raising questions about their suitability for broad policy application.

For next-generation EPCs, it's crucial to decide early whether recommendations are intended for standard application or as niche additions. Broad adoption requires meeting Criteria 4 (policy enforcement) and 5 (standardisation) to a high degree. Niche methods should focus more on Criteria 2 (new metrics), 3 (technology integration), and 6 (data quality).

Finally, the study questions **whether all EPC methods should meet the same criteria, given that different EPC frameworks have distinct goals and end-users. Categorising EPC methods into groupings may be a more practical approach to accommodate these differences while maintaining a core purpose.** This strategy would allow for a more flexible yet structured comparison between various EPC methods across Europe.

5.3 The harmonised XML format

The crossCert consortium analysed how the current and next-generation EPCs can be integrated into relevant regional or national databases.

Findings from this work are paramount to determine the possibilities of digitising and integrating EPCs in the national/regional databases as well as detect barriers and challenges preventing the integration.

All countries use XML files to manage EPC registration processes, but there are significant variations in data disclosure practices across EU member states. Even though professional energy assessors handle the registration, this has resulted in a non-harmonised EPC database environment. These inconsistencies are expected to persist as more countries develop their systems.

In terms of energy performance indicators, while results are widely disclosed, harmonisation is lacking because different countries use different metrics. CO₂ emissions are consistently reported across all databases, but energy demands, especially for domestic hot water (DHW), are less frequently disclosed. Heating and cooling demands are reported more often than DHW.

Data accessibility also varies. Around 70% of EPC databases provide public access, and 60% allow data extraction. However, achieving full accessibility is technically feasible by retrofitting existing systems, although data protection laws in some countries present a challenge. Despite this, all countries use XML file processing, which could support more uniform access if harmonisation efforts were made.

The overall quality of EPC data across the consortium is generally not reflective of best practices, although some countries are more advanced. To **improve harmonisation**, EPC databases should **fully disclose information directly from XML files, including more details on building envelope elements**, which are critical to the EU's renovation objectives. Additionally, while **CO₂ emissions** are widely reported, databases should also **include final energy, primary energy, and energy demands for heating, cooling, and DHW**, as these are easier for building owners to understand and are essential for improving energy efficiency awareness.

It is also recommended that EPC databases include recommendation measures, as less than half of the consortium currently shares this information, though it would benefit many stakeholders. **Cadastral identifiers and georeferenced data** should also be included to enhance the databases and improve **interoperability** with other administrative systems.

Achieving full digitalisation of EPC databases across the EU is crucial, and financial incentives could help facilitate this process. Finally, ensuring **full access to EPC data for users is vital**. Currently, only 40% of countries involved in crossCert provide full access, while others impose restrictions due to varying conditions and regulations. Addressing these gaps will be essential for creating a more harmonised and transparent EPC database system across Europe.

To enhance harmonisation among EU countries regarding EPCs, a **standardised set of energy performance parameters** has been proposed for inclusion in all databases. This initiative aims to ensure that participating countries disseminate similar information, which would allow stakeholders from various countries to benefit uniformly from these databases. The proposed information should be extracted from the XML files used by each assessed country for EPC registration.

Register Status	
Country:	---
Scale of the register:	National, regional or both
Beginning of the register:	--/--/---
Database access:	Public or only certifiers
Information extractable by the user:	xml, pdf, excel...

Building data	
Building identification	Address
Building year of construction:	----
Construction code used:	---
Climatic zone	Each country's designation
Habitable area	m ²
Net heated area	m ²
Building use	Residential
	Single family house
	Terraced house
	Multi-apartment building
	Tertiary sector
	Educational
	Office
	Sports hall
	Healthcare buildings
	Public entertainment buildings
	Community/Public assembly buildings
	Social housing
	Retail buildings
	Buildings for religious activities
	Public security buildings
	Others
	Industrial sector
	Industrial buildings
	Warehouses

Energy Performance data	
Is the building nZEB?	Yes or No
Final energy consumption	kWh/m ² year
Non-renewable primary energy	kWh/m ² year
Non-renewable primary energy rating	A, B, C, D, E, F, G
CO2 emissions	kgCO2/m ² year
CO2 emissions rating	A, B, C, D, E, F, G
Heating demand	kWh/m ² year
Heating demand rating	A, B, C, D, E, F, G
Cooling demand	kWh/m ² year
Cooling demand rating	A, B, C, D, E, F, G
Other	

Renewable energy contributions	
Heating renewable energy percentage	%
Cooling renewable energy percentage	%
DHW renewable energy percentage	%
Energy generator type	---
Other	

Potential energy efficiency interventions	
Envelope	Specify
Technical systems	Specify
Energy efficiency savings	%
Investment estimate cost	€
Payback period	years

Figure 5. Dataset disclosure proposal for European Union's EPC databases

In addition to the harmonised XML format, the recast of Annex V of the EPBD is essential, as it provides the European Commission's template for EPCs. Although EPC data disclosure already follows EPBD recast standards, there are additional points from Annex V that could be integrated into the harmonisation process.

The second phase of this initiative focuses on the generation of EPC databases, where the processing of collected information becomes crucial. The harmonised XML file will serve as a model to guide EU countries towards a common operational base. This processing phase aims to address concerns related to data protection expressed by some crossCert partners. By removing confidential data from the initial XML file, the remaining EPC information can be disseminated. It is recommended that the current weaknesses in data exploitation be addressed to enhance the effectiveness of existing databases.

While the proposed harmonised XML primarily targets the results of EPC assessments, it is also necessary to process building information to facilitate data disclosure. Key components include thermal envelope elements, technical systems, and operational conditions, which should be made available in the databases to meet stakeholders' needs effectively.

In conclusion, the quality assessment indicates that existing EPC databases generally maintain equivalent quality characteristics. Most registration processes across the assessed EU countries are managed by similar actors, and the majority of crossCert partners have successfully developed EPC repository structures that store comparable general information. However, the disclosure of building elements and energy indicators remains fragmented, highlighting the first significant lack of harmonisation. While CO₂ emissions are widely reported across all EPC platforms, this indicator can sometimes be misleading for stakeholders such as homeowners.

To address these challenges, a **common approach to processing EPC XML files** has been proposed as a harmonisation tool to **establish a common language for EPC databases**. Given that XML is the universal format for registering EPC data in the assessed countries, a **standardised processing procedure** is recommended. The sections to be disclosed widely in EPC databases include:

- general information (identification and cadastral data) to improve interoperability with other databases,
- detailed building datasets (including thermal envelopes, technical systems, and conservation status) to enhance information availability and usability
- comprehensive energy performance results (covering all available indicators) to promote a shared vocabulary among EU countries and
- renewable energy contributions to support EU objectives and improve market awareness.

Furthermore, it is recommended to include potential energy efficiency measures, detailing the proposals, costs, energy savings, and payback periods, to provide additional data for EU goals and foster real estate market awareness. **By implementing these recommendations, each EU member state can achieve harmonised information availability and standardised EPC file processing.** This groundwork will pave the way for interoperable EPC platforms, facilitating both national and international data interactions.

6 The human factor in convergence strategies

6.1 Stakeholder involvement

The involvement of stakeholders was a vital factor in the success of the crossCert project. From the early stages, partners identified key individuals to be interviewed, consulted, trained, and informed through various project activities, which helped establish the crossCert community. Following this, a detailed analysis and ranking of stakeholders was conducted to better understand their relevance to the project's objectives and gain insight into their perspectives. However, there were notable differences in the total number of stakeholders and the categories with the highest representation in each country. These variations may be attributed to factors such as the country's size and population, the specific role of each partner, or differences in national implementation schemes, which could necessitate the involvement of different stakeholders. The valorisation task also revealed that some partners chose to focus on the most critical stakeholders for the project's success, while others adopted a broader approach, including audiences also for dissemination and exploitation activities.

6.2 EPC design and user experience

crossCert consortium implemented an end-user survey across European countries and a subsequent workshop investigating user needs for EPCs. Individual outputs are discussed for those two different activities, followed by the additional findings and conclusions that can be achieved from the collective learning from multi-method user engagement.

The results of the survey as regards to harmonisation of EPCs in Europe are as follows:

Building users and architects

With reference to the diversity of the audience that EPCs are attempting to serve, a combination of graphical, tabular, and textual data was preferred for the information being delivered. This should also account for the different numerical ability and accessibility backgrounds of users of EPCs. When doing this, it was suggested that harmonisation of outputs across countries would be beneficial, including the use of clearly understood definitions; the inconsistent use of "primary energy" instead of "final energy" across different countries was provided as an example of where this can cause communication problems.

Policy-related

Advantages were seen in using both modelled and measured energy consumption when forming the output data. Users are likely to see the benefit of, and be interested in, measured data inasmuch as it reflects real users exhibiting real behaviour. For benchmarking and consistency of outputs, particularly when being used by regulators/policy-makers but also buyers, modelled data provides some level of harmonisation. Focussing on just one form of data was seen as placing too much reliance on the weakness of that information (e.g., modelling anomalies or peculiarities in real energy consumption data).

6.3 Achieving balance on assessor qualifications

As the results of other crossCert project studies have shown, the differences in EPC assessment processes and methodologies across European countries are significant, both in terms of the data used and the detail of the building assessments and tools used. It is therefore very important to find the optimal balance between the complexity of the assessment and the required knowledge and skills of EPC assessors, which is not the case in some countries as noted in an analysis by researchers at Heriot-Watt University in Edinburgh, UK. The EC's ambitions are to achieve better harmonisation of certificates and convergence of national assessment methodologies for energy performance and building certification

through the next generation of EPCs. Some of crossCert's recommendations might make assessments more accurate and reliable, but at the expense of applying methodologies with greater complexity. This means that a higher level of qualification of EPC assessors is needed and consequently undergoing mandatory training and verification of knowledge and skills. On the other hand, there are many buildings with simple technical systems where more sophisticated assessment is practically unnecessary. A sensible approach is to introduce different qualification level requirements for EPC assessors when assessing buildings of different complexity and develop different training programmes accordingly.

6.4 Towards people-centred EPCs

CrossCert's perspective on what people-centred EPC products and services actually means is that EPCs as social objects – not only exist within our society but also, they influence (and are influenced by) the socio-cultural dynamics in which they exist.

The diverse standards and traditions among EU countries, along with their unique political, economic, and socio-cultural situations, make it challenging to compare EPCs. This complexity is often viewed as a problem, especially with efforts to harmonise national and regional EPC systems to improve comparability across Europe. While some experts argue that this harmonisation can be beneficial, it's important to acknowledge its limitations. The ongoing debates about the best methods for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings highlight that, even over two decades since the initial introduction of EPCs in the EU, these discussions remain unresolved.

The **crossCert EPC Journey** outlines the steps involved in creating and utilising EPCs, focusing on the EPC itself while highlighting the key stakeholders involved at each stage. This framework emphasises the interactions among people and the practical aspects of EPC assessment and certification.

The **EPC Journey** infographic represents a generalised model and does not apply to any specific national EPC system. The crossCert project's goal is to compare EPCs and understand systemic differences, aiming for harmonisation across Europe. Each country's EPC Journey varies in the time allocated to different steps and in how those steps are executed, including the roles of responsible actors and available support services. The crossCert EPC Journey is designed as a structured tool for analysing existing EPC systems, facilitating comparisons among national schemes, and identifying potential improvements for harmonisation.

Figure 6. crossCert EPC Journey infographic (click to download full size version)

Figure 7. crossCert EPC Assessor's Journey infographic (click to download full size version)

Figure 8. crossCert EPC Design infographic (click to download full size version)

Figure 9. crossCert EPC Promotion and Marketing infographic (click to download full size version)

7 Summary of crossCert’s insights for harmonising EPCs across Europe

EPCs are fundamental instruments within the European Union’s strategy to achieve ambitious goals for energy savings and combat climate change. However, the effectiveness of EPCs is currently hampered by significant discrepancies in methodologies, formats, and implementation across member states.

Figure 10. Samples of different EPCs from cross-testing

The Status Quo of Harmonisation in EPC Ratings Through Cross-Testing

The CrossCert project involved extensive cross-testing of various European countries’ methodologies for EPCs to explore discrepancies, harmonise procedures, and learn from best practices. The project was structured around two key tests: C-building-testing (comparing methodologies across similar climates) and L-building-testing (local assessments focusing on performance gaps). The testing aimed to assess the feasibility of harmonising EPC processes across Europe by highlighting differences in calculation methods, data use, and the role of default values.

C-building-Testing involved cross-testing methodologies between countries with similar climates, focusing on specific types of buildings. The visiting country applied the host country’s EPC methodology to buildings in the testing country. For example, an Austrian building was tested using both Austrian and Slovenian EPC methods, with input guided by the hosting country. This process provided insight into how methodologies aligned or differed in aspects such as heating demand, primary energy consumption, and CO₂ emissions.

Key observations revealed variations in how different EPC methodologies treated inputs like local climate data, heating systems, and building orientation. Some countries, like Bulgaria, incorporated calibration steps using real energy consumption data, resulting in more accurate results. This contrasted with countries like the UK, where default values played a significant role. Figure 11 illustrates a comparative analysis of heating energy demand across testing countries, highlighting where correlations between methodologies were robust and where significant discrepancies existed.

Figure 11. Energy demand for heating ($\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{year}$) calculated with the EPC of the testing country versus energy demand for heating ($\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{year}$) calculated with the EPC of the visited country

In **L-building-Testing**, countries compared their EPC-generated energy consumption data with actual metered consumption for local buildings, investigating the "performance gap"—the difference between modelled and actual energy usage. This analysis was pivotal in identifying the robustness and accuracy of EPCs, particularly in residential versus non-residential buildings.

Countries like Denmark demonstrated a smaller performance gap (ranging from -1% to 22%) due to well-structured EPC guidelines and training. On the other hand, the UK experienced gaps as high as 233%, partly due to simplified EPC models that excluded electrical equipment and standardised occupancy schedules. Factors such as the use of default values and lack of building-specific data were common contributors to these discrepancies.

The key findings from cross-testing are the following:

- **Consistency in Energy Class Labels.** Despite variations in methodology, energy class labels (e.g., A+, B, etc.) for the same building were relatively consistent across countries (Figure 12). Buildings rated as highly energy-efficient in one country typically received similar ratings under other countries' EPC methods. This consistency is essential for formulating EU-wide building renovation policies and standardising renovation targets.
- **Performance Gap and Input Variables.** The study identified significant differences in the calculation of primary energy consumption and CO_2 emissions due to methodological diversity. Dynamic models and real-data calibration, like those in the UK for non-residential buildings, yielded more accurate results than static models. However, this accuracy came at the cost of higher data requirements and the need for better training for EPC issuers.
- **Role of Default Values.** Default values, commonly used across many EPC methodologies, streamlined processes but reduced the accuracy of certifications. Countries like the UK and Spain showed heavy reliance on these values, while Bulgaria's approach of adjusting the EPC to actual consumption data proved more accurate. The inconsistency in the application and transparency of default values was a significant obstacle to harmonisation.
- **Impact of Terminology.** A recurring issue was the lack of uniformity in language and calculation parameters across different countries' EPC methodologies. Terminological discrepancies hindered the comparability of results.

	Highly tailored									Highly standardised
Calculation methodology	Bulgaria	Poland	Slovenia	Croatia	Denmark	Spain	Greece	Malta	Austria	UK
Recommendations approach	Poland	Austria	Malta	Slovenia	Spain	Bulgaria	Croatia	Denmark	Greece	UK
Assessor background education	High requirement							Low requirement		
	Bulgaria	Croatia	Slovenia	Poland	Greece	Malta	Denmark	Spain	Austria	UK

Figure 12. Comparison of countries' approaches towards EPC calculation and EPC recommendations

EPC assessors

EPC assessor practices and training/skills are not the same. Assessors with different training/skill levels cannot perform the same assessments. They are also unlikely to accommodate new EPC metrics in the same way.

Figure 13. Level of training against level of complexity

Quality Control Frameworks Can Be Standardised, Whilst Allowing For Country-Specific Flexibility

The findings of the comparative exercises in crossCert were used to generate advice and frameworks for moving towards harmonisation of EPCs and applying next-generation EPCs across European countries. From this a framework is proposed for next-generation EPC quality control measures, as well as for categorising and comparing current and next-generation methodologies.

Considering all the differences discussed, any next-generation quality control mechanism needs to be able to address the variations in assessments and adapt to each country's specific needs. A framework for adapting quality control mechanisms to an EPC methodology is proposed in Figure 14 (Sayfekar and Jenkins, 2024b). This framework suggests that the quality control mechanism should depend on the calculation methodology, EPC software, EPC document, and assessor qualifications.

Figure 14. A framework for harmonisation of EPC quality control

Table 3. Harmonised quality control measures based on assessment approaches

Criteria	type	Suggested quality control measures	
Calculation methodology	Standardised	Validation rules in the software	
	Tailored	Validation rules in the software + Manual checks	
EPC software	Only accredited software	Validation rules in the software	
	Any software	Manual checks	
EPC document	Detailed	Automatic checks by the EPC database+ Manual checks	
	Simplified	Automatic checks by the EPC database	
EPC recommendations	Tailored	Savings calculated	Depending on the assessor's qualification/experienceàtargeted checks
		Savings not included	
	Standard	Savings calculated	Automatic checks by the EPC database+ Depending on the assessor's qualification/experienceàtargeted checks
		Savings not included	Automatic checks by the EPC database
Assessor qualification	Low requirement	Targeted checks+ Manual independent controls	
	High requirement	Manual independent controls	

Existing EPC databases

Key findings from the data collection process revealed that while most EPC databases are accessible online, issues such as language barriers and limited access restrict the usability of the data.

Key conclusions include:

- **EPC registration:** Most countries use energy assessors to submit data, with some relying on agencies or certifiers. XML and PDF files are standard, but some countries, like Poland, also allow manual entry.
- **Data disclosure:** While most databases provide general building information, additional non-energy data (e.g., geo-coordinates) would enhance usability. Disclosure of building elements and energy performance indicators is inconsistent, with Poland, Spain, and Bulgaria needing improvement. Slovenia and Austria lead in transparency. (See Figure 3.1.)
- **Recommendations:** Energy efficiency recommendations are only displayed in a few countries, limiting their usefulness in guiding investment decisions.
- **Digitalisation and interactivity:** Although digitalisation levels are high, data protection laws and restricted access limit full data availability in some countries. XML processing offers a technical pathway towards harmonised access to EPC data. (See Table 3.1.)

In summary, while EPC databases show promise, improvements in data accessibility, harmonisation, and disclosure are needed to fully unlock their potential for stakeholders and end-users.

Figure 15. Overview of EPC database disclosures across crossCert partner countries

8 Conclusions

The harmonisation guidelines proposed by crossCert project is a comprehensive set of recommendations for aligning EPCs, paving the way for improved comparability, transparency, and ultimately a more energy-efficient building stock within the EU.

CrossCert's guidelines

- 1. Regulations for Energy Performance Assessment and Certification.**
Develop a standardised EU-wide regulation for assessment and certification. This regulation should build upon existing best practices and incorporate regional specificities where necessary.
- 2. Input and Output Parameters of the EPC Process**
Establish a standardised list of mandatory input and output parameters for all EPCs across the EU.
- 3. EPC Checking and Verification Procedures**
Implement a harmonised system for EPC verification across the EU.
- 4. Bridging the Performance Gap**
Implement strategies to bridge the gap between predicted and actual energy consumption.
- 5. EPC Databases**
Develop a central EU EPC database with a standardised data structure and common protocols for data exchange.
- 6. Training and Certification of EPC Experts**
Establish a common EU framework for the training and certification of EPC experts.
- 7. Human Friendliness of the EPC**
Develop standardised and user-friendly EPC formats across the EU.
- 8. Marketing Buildings with Better EPCs**
Develop standardised and transparent marketing tools to highlight the financial and environmental benefits of buildings with strong EPC ratings.

CrossCert's testing revealed that while EPC methodologies across Europe share some similarities—particularly in energy class labels—significant methodological differences remain. The performance gap, inconsistent use of default values, and lack of standardised terms are major hurdles to harmonisation. Future efforts must focus on refining these areas to promote more reliable and comparable EPCs across the European Union. The pursuit of harmonisation in EPCs requires a comprehensive understanding of existing differences, clear definitions of goals, and careful consideration of cultural and practical factors across diverse national contexts. It highlights the need for tailored approaches that address the specific challenges and complexities inherent in each country's EPC framework.

The goal of harmonisation should not overshadow the need for flexible, country-specific approaches, as strict standardisation may limit effectiveness in individual countries. Nevertheless, some level of harmonisation could facilitate key objectives of the EPBD and enable the sharing of best practices. Addressing these variations in current EPC frameworks is crucial not only for current purposes but also for enhancing future applications of EPCs, ensuring they can adapt to diverse needs and innovations effectively.

This report emphasises the importance of recognising and respecting national differences in EPCs, especially when implementing top-down changes.

Harmonising EPCs across the EU requires a collaborative effort from policy makers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. By implementing the comprehensive recommendations outlined in this report, the EU can create a robust and reliable system for assessing and communicating building energy performance. This system will ultimately contribute to achieving the ambitious goals set forth in the EU's energy and climate policy agenda, paving the way for a more sustainable and energy-efficient building stock for future generations.

The evolution of next-generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) may differ from country to country. To develop these EPCs, it is essential to understand the needs of end-users. New EPC metrics should be designed with clear objectives, such as supporting One Stop Shops, and must focus on effective delivery and implementation. Furthermore, it is important to recognise the purposes and limitations of harmonisation in this context.

Clarification of Harmonisation: Before pursuing harmonisation of EPCs, it is essential to define what harmonisation means, as interpretations vary among stakeholders regarding the scope and components of EPCs.

Existing Variability: The EPBD acknowledges that EPCs can vary and does not require them to be identical. Differences in building stocks, climates, and technologies across countries are significant and must be considered.

Cultural Considerations: The cultural relationship between occupants and their buildings adds complexity to the idea of harmonisation. Factors like heating and cooling demands in different climates need to be taken into account when discussing harmonisation.

Aspects of Harmonisation: Harmonisation could relate to various aspects including EPC ratings, metrics, methodologies, assessment protocols, and the overall journey of EPCs, necessitating a deep dive into their methodologies to understand differences.

Diversity in Assessment Practices: The different backgrounds and trainings of EPC assessors across countries highlight a significant barrier to harmonisation, indicating that this aspect may need standardisation.

Baseline Understanding: Establishing a baseline for comparison is critical. Current EPC documentation shows aesthetic variations, and differences in calculation approaches must be understood, as they significantly impact the evaluation of energy performance.

Communication Methods: The methods of communicating energy efficiency improvements to building owners vary widely among EPCs, further complicating efforts for harmonisation.

Verification and Validation Frameworks: There is a need for robust verification and validation frameworks to determine effective categories and indicators for comparing EPCs, as well as to explore harmonisation of quality control mechanisms.

Recognition of Differences: While common indicators and outputs exist across EPCs, a detailed examination reveals substantial differences, underscoring the challenges faced in achieving true harmonisation.

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